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**Study of preparation and characterization
of silica sulfate and phosphate as catalysts
promotion for nitrite ion and their
applications of azo compounds
formation**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the Requirements
for the Master's Degree of Science in Chemistry.

By

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Dedication

To the noble martyrs.

*To those who have given me more than they ever gave .
themselves, and who continue to give: my mother, my
father, and my husband*

*To the candle that burned out too soon and left our
world Fatima.*

*To my beloved children, my dear sisters, and my
brothers.*

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In the Name of Allah, the Most Merciful, the Most Compassionate
All praise and gratitude be to Allah for everything, and for the blessing of
creating our Master Muhammad and his purified Household. May Allah's
peace and blessings be upon Muhammad and the family of Muhammad.

I would like to express my sincere thanks and appreciation to all
my teachers throughout my academic journey, from primary and
secondary school to my professors at Al-Muthanna University. My
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Abstract

In this study, silica was extracted from rice husk, and then it was stirred with diluted sulfuric acid and phosphoric acid for 24 h at room temperature. Different concentrations of acid have been loaded onto silica that's prepared, including X% RHASO_4 or X% RHAPO_4 , where X is: (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%). The prepared catalysts were characterized by several techniques including FT-IR, XRD, TGA / DTA, Nitrogen adsorption–desorption, SEM and TEM. The FT-IR showed that all expected functional groups were present for all catalysts. The XRD pattern showed a broadband at a 2θ angle of 22° pattern refer that the amorphous nature of the catalyst. The results of the TGA / DTA showed the catalysts were stable above 180°C . The images of scanning electron microscopy SEM showed the surface of the catalyst, including cylindrical shapes, some granular and some spherical, while the images of the electron microscope (TEM) showed nanoparticles of different shapes and different nanoparticles sizes, some of nanoparticles had a porous cavity layer and other had spherical shapes. The catalytic activity of each catalyst was studied as a generator carrier to nitrite ion in the preparation of nitrous acid which used to prepared diazonium salts. The catalysts (20% RHASO_4 and 20% RHAPO_4) were more efficient than other catalysts in the preparation of azo dyes. The activity of RHASO_4 and RHAPO_4 were analyzed at different loading of catalysts to obtain the best active loading. It was found that 20% RHASO_4 reached to its maximal of 65.5%, while it was reached to 75.5% by using 20% of RHAPO_4 . The reaction was carried out with 0.25 gm at 10°C from both catalysts.

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List of Symbols and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term
BET	Brunauer, Emmett and Teller
CPTES	3-chloropropyltriethoxysilane
DTA	Differential Thermal Analysis
FT-IR	Fourier Transform Infra-Red spectroscopy
RH	Rice Husk
RHA	Rice Husk Ash
RHASO ₄	Silica-Sulfate
5% RHASO ₄	Silica-5% Sulfate
10% RHASO ₄	Silica-10% Sulfate
15% RHASO ₄	Silica-15% Sulfate
20% RHASO ₄	Silica-20% Sulfate
RHAPO ₄	Silica-Phosphate
5% RHAPO ₄	Silica-5% Phosphate
10% RHAPO ₄	Silica-10% Phosphate
15% RHAPO ₄	Silica-15% Phosphate
20% RHAPO ₄	Silica-20% Phosphate
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
Si-OH	Silanol group
Si-O-Si	Siloxane group
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analyses
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction

Chapter One

Introduction

1.0 Overview

Design characterization, production and applications of structures, devices and systems by controlling shape and size at nanometer scale is refers to nanotechnology [1]. Nanostructured materials of various types and forms are formulated in a variety of novel ways and have been increasingly subjected to many types of chemical and physical analysis [2]. Around a third of European public spending on nanoscience and nanotechnology is intended to create applications that will improve existing products. In the medium to long term, the goal is to achieve major improvements centering on the construction of entirely new applications, which will mark the beginning of a new technological cycle [3].

Since nanomaterial systems contain a relatively large amount of surface or interface area, it should be natural to characterize those using tools that designed to analyze such surfaces and interfaces. They have found that nanoparticles and other nanostructured materials present a variety of analytical challenges [2]. Nanomaterials include nanoparticles, nanoclusters, nanocrystals, nanotubes, nanofibers, nanowires, nanorods, nanofilms, etc. [4]. Nanoparticles could be Inorganic nanoparticles, polymeric nanoparticles, solid lipid nanoparticles, etc. [5]. Nanoscience and nanotechnology are near the forefront of exciting areas of science and technology and as a result, a significant amount of the world's resources available for research has focused in areas broadly classified as "Nano" [2]. Nanotechnology applications use fewer raw materials, save time and energy to create smaller, lighter, cheaper, faster and smart functional devices [6]. Nanotechnology is the manipulation of matter on the molecular and atomic levels. It has the potential to bring enormous changes into the many different fields [7].

1.1 Catalyst

Catalysis is the key to chemical transformations, most industrial syntheses and nearly all biological reactions require catalysts [8]. Catalysts are substances that can be added to the reaction to increase the rate of the reaction and decrease the reaction's time [9]. Furthermore, catalysis is the most important material in environmental protection [8].

Figure 1.1: Energy diagram for a chemical reaction [10].

The important rules in the design of any catalyst should be its ease of synthesis; the catalyst recoverable, reusable and environment friendly [11]. A catalyst is a substance that changes the rate of a chemical *reaction*, *but doesn't* in nuance the thermodynamic equilibrium between the reactants and products [12]. The numerous catalysts known today can be classified according to various *criteria*, *i.e. structure*, *composition*, area of application, or state of aggregation. There are two large groups of catalyst: heterogeneous catalysts and homogeneous catalysts (Scheme 1.1) [8].

Scheme 1.1: General classification of catalysts [8].

1.2 Heterogeneous catalysts

Heterogeneous catalysis plays a key role in the manufacture of essential products in the areas of agriculture and pharmaceuticals, in the production of polymers and numerous essential materials. Understanding of heterogeneous catalysts is advancing rapidly, especially by using the latest characterization methods on these relatively complex effect materials [13]. Among heterogeneous catalysis, solid acids, prepared by adsorbing mineral acids onto a solid surface, are introduced mainly to replace highly corrosive mineral acids in the reaction medium and used in many important large-scale industrial processes [14, 15]. One of the ultimate goals for organic reactions is to reduce the use of harmful organic solvents and use of heterogeneous catalysts instead of homogeneous catalysts, because of the

environment and economic regulations [16] [17]. The advantage and main characteristic of the heterogeneous catalysts such as: the separation of the catalyst from the reaction mixture is simplified [18, 19, 20], the solid structure avoids the aggregation to the active catalyst [21], high thermal stability, Resistance solubility in organic solvents, The ability of stored for a long time, and high selectivity [22].

1.3 Rice husk ash (RHA)

Rice husk (RH) is one of the most widely available agricultural wastes in many rice producing countries around the world [23]. RHA is left after the burning of RH. It can cause environmental pollution, as its difficult disposal. Hence its proper reuse is necessary; it is mainly composed of carbon and silica [24]. Burning the husk under controlled temperature below 800 °C can produce ash with silica mainly in amorphous form [25]. Fig. (1.1) shows the common products from RH.

Fig 1.2: Common - products from RH [23].

1.3.1 The properties of RHA

Unique characteristics of RH in comparison with other agricultural residues such as high silica contents, high porosity, lightweight and very high external surface area make it a valuable material for industrial applications [26]. The best application of RH appears as a good source of silica. RH upon burning yields 14-20% ash, which is silica in the crystalline form together with trace amounts of metallic impurities [27]. The silica content of the ash was found to be $\geq 95\%$. Many catalysts have been prepared via sol-gel technique using silica from RHA as a support [28]. By pretreatment methods and controlling the burning conditions like temperature and time, amorphous silica with high purity and ultrafine particle size can be produced. The combustion temperature and time are two important factors to define whether the silica in the RHA remains amorphous or becomes crystalline [27]. Typical analysis of RH was shown in Table (1.1).

Table 1.1: Typical Analysis of RH [23].

Property	Range
Bulk density (kg/m^3)	96 – 160
Hardness (Mohr's scale)	5-6
Ash %	22 – 29
Carbon %	~ 35
Hydrogen %	4 – 5
Oxygen %	31 – 37
Nitrogen %	0.23 - 0.32
Sulphur %	04 - 0.08
Moisture	8-9

1.3.2 Application of RH

The risk of scarcity of natural resources and the increasingly severe issues around environmental pollution has highlighted the need for materials with established properties for specific purposes. In this regard, the development of new, low-impact materials is essential in the attempt to minimize environmental problems [29]. The scheme (1.2) shows the important application of RH in different fields.

_____Scheme 1.2: Applications of RH [26]._____

The use of recycled materials, apart from by products that until recently were considered industrial waste, emerges as an interesting alternative to mitigate environmental issues, such measures reduce the amount of raw materials extracted from the environment, promoting the use and adding value to waste that otherwise would be disposed of in industrial landfills. A good example of such environmental effort is the use of RHA [29].

Fig. 1.3: Appearance of RHA and extracted silica by different treatment schemes: (a) Raw RH. (b) Extracted silica by combustion of untreated RH at 600 °C. (c) Extracted silica from treated RH in 1 N HCl acid followed by combustion at 600 °C [27].

Scheme 1.3: Applications of RHA [30].

1.4 The Using of Silica from RH as a Support

Silicon is one of the most resources widely used in modern technology. Industrially silicon is the basis of semiconductors, glasses, ceramics, insulators, moisture shields, fillers, solar cells, etc. These devices require pure silica, which is currently produced by smelting and high end techniques. Development of a simple low energy and cost effective production of pure silica is desirable and welcome by many industrial application [31]. Silica (SiO_2) is one of the valuable inorganic multipurpose chemical compounds. It can exist in gel, crystalline and amorphous forms [32]. Silica offers many advantages to chemical processes such as improved selectivity and ease of separation from reaction mixture, reducing the number of process stages and generation of wastes [33]. Amorphous silica has a non-ordered structure with irregular channels and pore diameter that can broadly vary [34]. Silica was used as a supporter to saccharine as in the scheme (1.4) [33]. The catalyst used successfully for esterification reaction. The application of this catalyst was used as a model for biofuel production [35].

Scheme 1.4: The reaction Scheme for the immobilization of Sac onto RHACCl to form RHAC-Sac [35].

Melamine was immobilized onto silica via 3-chloropropyltriethoxysilane. The resulting catalyst was designated as RHAPrMela. The catalyst was used for esterification of fatty acid with methanol [36].

Scheme 1.5: The reaction sequence and the possible structures for RHAPrMela [36].

7-Amino-1-naphthalene sulfonic acid was immobilized onto silica via a simple sol-gel technique to form strong Brønsted acid catalyst [28]. Scheme (1.6) shows the multiple steps for the catalyst reaction. The catalyst structure was identified by different characterizations.

Scheme 1.6: The reaction sequence for the synthesis of RHANPSO₃H [28].

Sulfanilic acid was immobilized onto RHA via 3-chloropropyltriethoxy-silane to form an acidic solid catalyst denoted as RHAPhSO₃H. Scheme (1.7) shows the reaction synthesis bath. The catalyst was used in the alkylation of phenol [37].

Scheme 1.7: The reaction sequence for the synthesis of RHAPhSO₃H [37].

In the scheme (1.8) a simple route is demonstrated for the efficient immobilization of silica with 1-(N-acetylphenylalanine)-ruthenium (III) complex. This catalyst was labelled a RHAPhe–Ru. The catalytic performance of RHAPhe–Ru was tested in the esterification of ethyl alcohol [38].

Scheme 1.8: the reaction sequence for the synthesis of RHAPhe–Ru [38].

1.5 Solid Sulfuric acid

The use of heterogeneous solid acid catalysts is important to the development of sustainable chemical processes [17]. Sulfuric acid is a dense clear liquid. It is used for making fertilizers, leaching metallic ores, and manufacturing a myriad of chemicals. Worldwide, about 200 million ton of sulfuric acid is consumed per year. The raw material for sulfuric acid is SO_2 gas [39]. Sulfuric acid can be used as catalyst. In recent years; the use of silica supported sulfuric acid has received considerable attention in the field of organic synthesis, where it has been widely used as a versatile heterogeneous catalyst [40]. Sulfonic-acid-functioned Brønsted acidic ionic liquids have been considered as a promising dual solvent-catalyst for numerous applications [41].

1-Butylimidazole (BIm) was successfully immobilized onto RHA via 3-chloropropyltriethoxysilane to produce RHABIm-Cl. The chlorine was easily replaced with sulphate anion at room temperature as in the scheme (1.9) [42].

Scheme 1.9: The reaction sequence for the synthesis of RHABIm-Cl and RHABIm-HSO₄ [42].

Solid urea sulfate onto silica extracted from RHA [43]. The chloride groups were reacted with urea by a nucleophilic substitution reaction. The resulting silica with urea (which had amine end groups) was sulfated with diluted sulfuric acid to produce a novel solid state catalyst designated RHAUR-SO₄H, as shown in the scheme (1.10) [43].

Scheme 1.10: The reaction sequence and the possible structure for RHAUR-SO₄H catalyst as it was suggested by spectroscopic analyses [43].

1.6 Solid Phosphoric acid

Phosphoric acid used as catalyst, since the early 1930s. Solid phosphoric acid catalysts have been industrially used for light olefin oligomerization to produce polymer gasoline, which is an important step in the promotion of gasoline quality [44]. Solid phosphoric acid (SPA) catalysts are widely used in the industry [45].

The main crystalline phases of the catalyst are silicon phosphates. The analysis of the silicon phosphate composition helps to recognize the reason for the variation of the catalytic performance and guide the design and the optimization of the solid phosphoric acid catalyst [44].

1-Butylimidazole was successfully immobilized onto RHA via 3-chloropropyltriethoxy-silane to produce RHABIm-Cl. The chlorine was easily replaced with phosphate anion at room temperature, as shown in the scheme (1. 12).

Scheme 1.11 the reaction sequence for the synthesis of RHABIm-Cl and RHABIm- H_2PO_4 [42]

1.7 Azo Dyes

Azo compounds are a class of chemical compounds that is continuously receiving attention in scientific research. They are usually strongly colored compounds which can be intensely yellow, red, orange, blue or even green, depending on the exact structure of the molecule [46]. When describing a dye molecule, nucleophiles are referred to as auxochromes, while the aromatic groups are called chromophores together; the dye molecule is often described as a chromogen [47]. As a result of their colour, azo compounds are tremendous importance as dyes and also as pigments for a long time. In fact, about half of the dyes in industrial use today are azo dyes, which are mostly prepared from diazonium salts [46]. Synthesis of most azo dyes involves diazotization of a primary aromatic amine, followed by coupling with one or more nucleophiles. Most importantly, the groups that invariably confer colour are the azo ($-\text{N}=\text{N}-$) and nitroso ($-\text{N}=\text{O}$) while the other groups actually do so under certain circumstances [46][48]. Amino- and hydroxy- groups are commonly used coupling components because of the diversity of dye components available for synthesis, a large number of structurally different azo dyes exist and are used in industry [47]. Azo colorings are the most versatile class of dyes. Their

structure has been intensely studied and many spectral data analyses have already been reported. The dyes have been most widely used in fields such as dyeing textile fibers, biomedical studies, advanced applications in organic synthesis and high technology areas like lasers, liquid crystalline displays, electro-optical devices and ink-jet printer [49].

Furthermore, Azo dyes are known for their medicinal importance and to be involved in a number of biological reactivity such as inhibition of DNA, RNA and protein synthesis, carcinogenesis and nitrogen fixation. In broader sense, the azo dyes constitute the largest diverse group of all the synthetic colorants [50]. The adsorption properties of different dyes were reported. Organic dyes have also been reported as effective corrosion inhibitors of mild steel in different media [49]. Furthermore, azo dyes have been studied widely because of their excellent thermal and optical properties in applications such as optical recording medium toner ink-jet printing, and oil-soluble light fast dyes. Recently, azo compounds as organic dyes have also attracted attention due to their interesting electronic features in connection with their application for molecular memory storage, nonlinear optical elements and organic photoconductors [46]. Nomenclature of azo depending on the number of azo groups, the azo dyes are called monoazo, disazo, trisazo, tetraazo, etc., dyes, and those with three or more azo groups, polyazo dyes [51].

1.8 Diazonium salt

The synthesis of diazonium salts is historically an important transformation extensively utilized in dye manufacture. However the highly reactive nature of the diazonium functionality has additionally led to the development of many new reactions including several carbon-carbon bond forming processes. It is therefore highly desirable to determine optimum conditions for the formation of diazonium

compounds [52]. Diazonium salt is any group of salts which its formula is "ArN₂X", in that "Ar represents any aryl group" it can detect that the positive part is the diazonium and the negative part is the anion. Diazonium salts have many pharmaceutical uses and mainly used in formation of dyes and synthesize aryl halides by Sandmeyer reaction [53].

Chemical functional groups containing nitrogen are ubiquitous across the physical and biological sciences. However, it is notable that there are still very few methods for the activation and use of a C–N bond as a tool for the construction of more complex molecules, with the formation and use of diazo and diazonium compounds being the most widely adopted process to achieve this goal. However, there are several drawbacks to the use of diazonium compounds, not the least of which include the associated safety hazards that are well particularly documented [54]. Indeed the diazonium salts are easy to synthesize from the corresponding amines giving a large choice in substitution particularly in para of the aryl diazonium cation [55].

Aryl diazonium salts are important intermediates. They are prepared in cold (0 ° to 10 °C) aqueous solution, and generally react with nucleophiles with loss of nitrogen. Some of the more commonly used substitution reactions are shown in the following diagram. Since the leaving group (N₂) is thermodynamically very stable, these reactions are energetically favored (scheme 1.13).

Scheme 1.12: Reaction of aryl diazonium [56].

In 1858, several prominent named reactions associated with diazonium salts have evolved throughout the development of more than one century (Scheme 1.14).

Scheme 1.13: Brief history of diazonium salts [57].

Objectives of this Study

- 1- Preparation of solid catalyst of sulfuric acid and Phosphoric acid as generator of nitrite ion.
- 2- Characterization the properties of prepared catalysts by spectroscopic techniques.
- 3- Estimation of catalyst influence theory, application of diazonium salt production at different operating conditions.

Chapter Two

Experimental Part

2.1 Raw Materials and Chemicals

All chemicals were used directly without purification. The RH was collected from a rice mill in Samawah City, Iraq. Table (2-1) below, shows the chemicals used and their purity. The manufacturing companies were also shown.

Table 2.1: The chemicals were used by the percentage of their purity and company's supplier.

Entry	Chemicals	Company	Purity%
1	p-Aminophenol	Sigma- Aldrich	$\geq 98\%$
2	Aniline	GCC	99.5
3	n-Butanol	R&M chemical	99
4	Ethanol absolute	GFS Chemical	99.8
5	Methanol	Scharlau	99.9
6	1-Naphthol	SCR	≥ 99.0
7	Nitric acid	System	65
8	p-Nitrophenol	Sigma- Aldrich	$\geq 99\%$
9	Phosphoric acid	GCC	85
10	1-Propanol	R&M chemical	99
11	Sodium hydroxide	System	99
12	Sodium nitrite	BDH Chemical	96
13	Sulfuric acid	Sigma- Aldrich	98

2.2 Extraction of Silica from RH

The RH was used as a source of amorphous silica. The extraction of silica from RH was done as according to [58]. The RH was washed with a copious amount of water and rinsed with distilled water. After 24 h drying at the laboratory temperature, the RH was stirred with 1.0 M nitric acid for about 24 h. Then the RH was washed with water and drying at 110 °C. The cleaned RH was burning in a muffle furnace at 800 °C for 6 h. Scheme (2-1) was shown the changes in the physical form of RH. Where step 1 on the arrow indicates the washing process of RH more than six times, while step 2 refers RH after the stirrer with HNO₃, and finally step 3 indicates the calcination at 800 °C for 6 h. The product was labeled as RHA.

Scheme 2.1: Extraction of silica from RH.

2.3 Catalyst Preparation

2.3.1 Preparation of Silica-Sulfuric Acid

About 25 mL of 5% H_2SO_4 was added to 3.0 gm of RHA, in a round bottom flask and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at the laboratory temperature. The mixture was filtered and the precipitate was collected. The precipitate was dried at 110 °C for 24 h and then grinds well. By following similar strategy different loading acid onto silica was prepared and labeled as 10% RHASO_4 , 15% RHASO_4 , and 20% RHASO_4 . As shown in the schematic (2-2).

Scheme 2.2: Loading of sulfuric acid onto RHA.

2.3.2 Preparation of Silica-Phosphoric Acid

About 25mL of 5% H_3PO_4 was added to 3.0 gm of RHA, in a round bottom flask and stirred for 24 h at the laboratory temperature. The mixture was filtered. The precipitate was dried at 110 °C for 24 h and then grinds well. By following similar strategy different loading of phosphoric acid onto silica was prepared: (10%RH APO_4 , 15%RH APO_4 , and 20%RH APO_4). As shown in the following scheme (2-3).

Scheme 2.3: Loading of phosphoric acid onto RHA.

2.4 Catalytic Reactions

2.4.1 Catalyst Activity on Synthesis of Azo Dye

The required catalyst (0.1 gm) was mixed with aniline (1.0 mL, 10.9 mmole) in water (5.0 mL). To this solution, a solution of NaNO₂ (0.69 gm, 10 mmole) in water (5.0 mL) was added at 0-5 °C and the resulted solution was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The catalyst was removed by simple filtration. After that, a solution of α-naphthol (0.2 gm, 1.3 mmole) in an aqueous solution of NaOH (2.0 mL, 1.0 M) was added to filtrated. The reaction mixture was then left for 1.0 hour before being filtered and the filtrate was acidified. The precipitate azo dye was collected by filtration.

Final yield was calculated by using an equation: $\text{Yield \%} = (W_{\text{ex.}} / W_{\text{theo.}}) \times 100 \%$, where ($W_{\text{ex.}}$) is the experimental weight, ($W_{\text{theo.}}$) is the theoretical weight.

2.4.2 The Optimization of Sulfuric Acid Loading

The catalytic activity with the different mass of catalysts (5%RHASO₄, 10%RHASO₄, 15%RHASO₄, and 20%RHASO₄) was studied by using the same procedure as in section 2.4.1.

2.4.3 The Optimization of Phosphoric Acid Loading

The preparation of catalysts with different loading of phosphoric acid: (5%RHAP₄O₄, 10%RHAP₄O₄, 15%RHAP₄O₄, and 20%RHAP₄O₄), was studied by using the same procedure as in section 2.4.1.

2.4.4 The Optimization of Catalysts Mass

The catalytic activity with different mass of catalysts (0.10, 0.15, 0.20, and 0.25 gm) was studied by using the same procedure as in section 2.4.1. The reaction was carried at 5 °C besides using 20%RHASO₄ or 10 °C besides using 20%RHAP₄O₄.

2.4.5 The Optimization of Reaction Temperature

The catalytic activity at different temperatures (5, 10, and 15 °C) was studied by following the same procedure as in section 2.4.1. The reaction was carried out by using 0.25 gm (optimum mass) of the catalyst over 20%RHASO₄, and 20%RHAP₄O₄.

2.4.6 The Optimization of Reaction Solvent

The catalytic activity with different solvent such as (water, methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, and n-butanol) was studied in the same produce in section 2.4.1. The high yield of 4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol is the key to know the best solvent which is suitable for this reaction in presence catalyst.

2.4.7 The reusability of the Catalysts

The catalysts were reused multi-times under the optimum reaction conditions. The dyes production was first run with the fresh catalyst to complete the reaction. After that, the catalyst was isolated and dried at 110 °C for 24 h. Then this isolated catalyst was reused for the second run.

2.5 Physical–Chemical Characterization

2.5.1 Fourier Transferring Infrared (FTIR) Spectral Analysis

FT-IR spectroscopy samples were done using KBr disks at the wave number range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹. FT-IR were measured by using (Shimadzu-8400S), the measurement was done at the College of Science, AL-Muthanna University, Iraq.

2.5.2 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) /Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) of RHASO₄

TGA was performed using a TGA /DTA instrument, a catalyst was heated from 40 °C to 800 °C at a heating rate of 40 °C/min, all samples are under nitrogen flow. TGA /DTA were using (Perkin-Elmer 4000). The measurement was done at the college of science, AL-Muthanna University, Iraq.

2.5.3 Nitrogen Adsorption–Desorption

Nitrogen adsorption–desorption analysis of surface area and pore size were done by saturating the sample with vapor pressure 86.245 kPa, adsorption cross section area 0.162 nm², adsorptive N₂, and 77 K temperature. The pore diameter and pore size distribution of the materials were obtained from the adsorption isotherms, were measurements at the University of Tehran, Iran.

2.5.4 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Sample preparation is an essential part of the technique. As a rule of thumb TEM requires samples with a thickness of less than 100 nm. They also need to withstand the exposure to the high energy electron beam. The sample was suspended in absolute ethanol, which is unreactive with the sample. After that a drop of the mixture was moved to disc and a solvent evaporates to leave the sample ready for investigation. The TEM has been at the University of Tehran, Iran.

2.5.5 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was recorded by using (FEI Nova SEM 450). In SEM technique a focused beam of high-energy electrons was scanned over the surface of a material to give topographical images. The SEM was measured at the University of Tehran, Iran.

2.5.6 X-ray Diffraction Patterns (XRD)

The powder X-ray diffraction patterns of samples were measured under the following conditions: X-ray tube: target (Cu), voltage 40.0 kv and current 30.0 mA. The diffraction angle was scanned in the 2θ range, 5° to 80° at scan speed: 8.000 deg/ min. XRD analysis was recorded using (Shimadzu 6000). The measurement was done at the college of Education for Pure Science (Ibn al-Haitham), University of Baghdad, Iraq.

Chapter Three

Results and

Discussion

3.1 Preparation of RHASO₄

The description of the direct synthesis of sulfuric acid onto RHA to produce a nano-silica catalyst. The preparation of the nano catalyst was carried out by the reaction between RHA with dilute sulfuric acid at room temperature. The catalyst is characterized by many techniques to prove its structure. A proposed structure for nano silica sulfuric acid showed in the scheme 3.1.

Scheme 3.1: Structure of nano silica sulfuric acid [59, 60]

3.1.1 Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopic of RHASO₄

The FT-IR spectrum of RHASO₄ showed in Fig. 3.1 (a, b, c, and d), while table 3.1 shows the vibration of functional groups. The silanol group was observed at 3444-3390 cm⁻¹ in Fig. 3.1 (a). In Fig. 3.1 (b, c, and d) for other loading of 5%RHASO₄ (10, 15, 20%) the silanol groups were observed at 3441 cm⁻¹, 3458-3421 cm⁻¹ and 3416 cm⁻¹, respectively. The strong band at 1099 cm⁻¹ was due to the stretching vibration of Si-O-Si. The SO₄ functional group was shown in between 1130-1080, 680-610 cm⁻¹ [61].

Table 3.1 FT-IR results of RHASO₄.

Functional groups	Vibration of 5%RHASO ₄ cm ⁻¹	Vibration of 10%RHASO ₄ cm ⁻¹	Vibration of 15%RHASO ₄ cm ⁻¹	Vibration of 20%RHASO ₄ cm ⁻¹
Si-OH	3444-3390	3441	3458-3421	3416
Si-O-Si	1099	1100	1100	1095
Moisture in SiO ₂	1651	1643	1639	1649
S -O stretch	794	885-792	891-802	885-794

Fig. 3.1: FT-IR spectrum of (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%RHASO₄).

3.1.2 Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) /Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) for RHASO₄

Figures 3.2 (a, b, c, and d) show the TGA/DTA graphs of the 5%RHASO₄, 10%RHASO₄, 15%RHASO₄, and 20%RHASO₄. The TGA analysis of 5%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (a) showed three characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 2.1% at 163 °C due to the loss of surface absorbed water. The second mass loss was 2.7% at 299 °C. The third mass loss was 1.5% at 580 °C. The second and third mass losses were indicated the losing of sulfuric acid loaded onto silica. The calculation of mass loss showed that only 4.2% of catalyst mass were lost. This indicates that our method was successfully loaded \approx 5% of sulfuric acid onto silica.

The TGA analysis of 10%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (b) showed three characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was about 3.0% at 169 °C as a result of loss surface absorbed water. The second mass loss was 6.6% at 290°C. The third mass loss was 1.8% at 590 °C. While the TGA analysis of 15%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (c) showed three characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 3.4% at 141 °C. The second mass loss was 9.5% at 251°C. The third mass loss was 2% at 553 °C. The total mass losses of this catalyst were 14.9% this mass very closed to the experiment percentage of H₂SO₄ added to the silica. TGA analysis of 20%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (d) showed four characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 5.6% at 115 °C. The second mass loss was 9.7% at 243 °C. The third mass loss was 6.5% at 436 °C. And the four mass loss was 0.7% at 680 °C.

The DTA curve was shown in Fig. 3.2 (a, b, c, and d), the DTA curve for 5%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (a) shows three exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs in the range of 40-228 °C with maximum at 163 °C. It could be reflected the loss of absorbed water. The second exothermic occurs at 228-387 °C with maximum of 299 °C, and the third exothermic occurs in the range of 520-660 °C with maximum 580 °C. The DTA curve for 10%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (b) shows three exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs in the range of 40-219 °C with maximum at 169 °C. It was due to the loss of absorbed water.

The second exothermic occurs at 219-372 °C with maximum of 290 °C, and the third exothermic occurs in the range of 372-630 °C with maximum of 590 °C. The DTA curve for 15%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (c) shows three exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs at 40 -188 °C with maximum of 141 °C. The second exothermic occurs at 188-344 °C with maximum of 251 °C, and the third exothermic occurs in the range of 500-600 °C with maximum of 553 °C. The DTA curve for 20%RHASO₄ in Fig. 3.2 (d) shows three exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs at 40 -189 °C with maximum of 115 °C. While the second exothermic occurs at 189-304 °C with maximum of 243 °C, and the third exothermic occurs at 304-488 °C with maximum of 436 °C.

Fig.3.2 (a): TGA / DTA for 5% RHASO₄.

Fig.3.2 (b): TGA / DTA for 10% RHASO₄.

Fig.3.2 (c): TGA / DTA for 15% RHASO₄.

Fig.3.2 (d): TGA / DTA for 20% RHASO₄.

3.1.3 Nitrogen adsorption– desorption for different loading of RHASO₄

The N₂ adsorption analysis Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method is still used for the determination of surface area [62]. The N₂ adsorption– desorption analysis showed the specific surface area of 20% RHASO₄ was 8.20 m² gm⁻¹, the specific surface area of 15% RHASO₄ was 40.03 m² gm⁻¹, while the specific surface area of 10% RHASO₄ 53.6 m² gm⁻¹, and the specific surface area of 5% RHASO₄ was 69.6 m² gm⁻¹. Fig. 3.3 (a, and b) shows that the nitrogen adsorption isotherm of 5% RHASO₄ and 10% RHASO₄, in both the shapes of hysteresis loops was type H1. This associated with porous materials exhibiting a narrow distribution of relatively uniform (cylindrical-like) pores [63].

The other catalysts 15% RHASO₄ and 20% RHASO₄ show isotherms type H3 hysteresis loops. This was not exhibiting any limiting adsorption at the high P/P_o . This behavior caused by the existence of non-rigid aggregates of plate-like particles or assemblages of slit-shaped pores and in principle should not be expected to provide a reliable assessment of either the pore size distribution or the total pore volume [63].

The pore size distribution of 5% RHASO₄ was found 38.27 nm. The pore size distribution of 10% RHASO₄ was found 16.41 nm, while the pore size distribution of 15% RHASO₄ was found 15.29 nm, and the pore size distribution of 20% RHASO₄ was found 12.15 nm, which was in the nanoporous scale. At the higher loading the pore diameter was decreased. This could be due to the increase of acid concentration led to close the pore and become narrow. The information on the Nitrogen adsorption– desorption analysis was shown in Table 3.2, and Fig 3.3.

Fig.3.3. The nitrogen adsorption– desorption isotherm of (a) 5%RHASO₄, (b) 10%RHASO₄, (c) 15%RHASO₄, and (d) 20%RHASO₄.

Table 3.2: The nitrogen adsorption– desorption parameter for different loading of RHASO_4 .

Sample	Surface area (m^2/gm)	Average pore diameter (nm)	Average pore volume (cm^3/gm)
5% RHASO_4	6.10	38.27	0.05
10% RHASO_4	29.97	16.41	0.12
15% RHASO_4	40.19	15.29	0.154
20% RHASO_4	49.99	12.15	0.15

3.1.4.1 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) for 5% RHASO_4

As shown in Fig 3.4 (a, b, c and d) the TEM images for 5% RHASO_4 showed the particles were irregular and correlated cluster grids were obtained. Fig. 3.4 (e) TEM image of 5% RHASO_4 showed nano platelets of different layer in thicknesses. Furthermore, Fig. 3.4 (f) TEM of 5% RHASO_4 showed multi-walled nano rod appears in the form with one layer. In addition, some spherical particles were found randomly distributed.

Fig. 3.4: The TEM images for 5%RHASO₄ at different magnification.

3.1.4.2 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) for 10%RHASO₄

The TEM of 10% RHASO₄ Fig. 3.5 (a, b, and c) shows cluster particles, also shows spherical nanoparticles. These particles were arranged randomly. In Fig. 3.5 (d) spherical particles were shown. Fig. 3.5 (d) the TEM image for 10%RHASO₄ showed a lot of spherical shapes. These nanoparticles were found randomly distributed.

Fig. 3.5: The TEM images for 10%RHASO₄.

3.1.4.3 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) for 15%RHASO₄

Fig. 3.6 (a, b, c, and d) shows the TEM images of 15% RHASO₄. All TEM images showed spherical shapes irregular distributed.

Fig. 3.6: The TEM images for 15% RHASO₄ at different magnification.

3.1.4.4 Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) for 20%RHASO₄

Fig. 3.7 shows the TEM images of 20% RHASO₄ at different magnification. The images show the existence of spherical shapes in nano size.

Fig. 3.7: The TEM images for 20%RHASO₄ at different magnification. The TEM images show spherical nanoparticles in varying numbers and sizes.

3.1.5.1 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for 5%RHASO₄

Fig. 3.8(a, b, c, and d) shows the SEM of 5%RHASO₄. The surface was rough and cylindrical shapes were seen arranged randomly onto surface. In Fig. 3.8 (b) the pores were seen onto surface. In Fig. 3.8 (c) a spherical spots were clearly seen with different nano size.

Fig. 3.8: The SEM images for 5%RHASO₄.

3.1.5.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for 10%RHASO₄

In Figure 4.9(a, b, c, and d) shows the SEM of 10%RHASO₄. A granule surface was seen in Fig.3.9 (a, and b). The particles were spherical in shape with different nano size. Fig. 3.9 (c, and d) moth surface with micro tubs were seen. These tubs were collected with each other's. The tubs seem to be hollow and this may have important character beside it has been used as catalyst.

Fig. 3.9: SEM image of 10%RHASO₄.

3.2.5.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for 15%RHASO₄

The SEM of 15%RHASO₄ was give in Fig. 3.10 (a, b, c, and d). The surface shown micro tubes, the tubes were hollow and collected with each others in groups. Fig. 3.10 (c) shows the SEM image nanofiber particles. Fig. 3.10 (d) the random distribution of rough particles were seen.

Fig. 3.10: Shows the SEM images topography to surface of 15%RHASO₄.

3.1.5.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for 20%RHASO₄

The SEM of 20%RHASO₄ was given in Fig. 3.11(a, b, c, and d). In all images the catalyst shows nano rock arranged in the surface. These rocks have different nano size and shapes. The pores were clearly seen.

Fig. 3.11: The SEM images for 20%RHASO₄.

3.1.6 X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis for RHASO₄

XRD pattern analysis is used to monitor the scattering intensity of the X-ray beam at the angle of fall and scattering. Fig. 3.12 (a, b, c, and d) shows XRD-pattern of (5, 10, 15, and 20) %RHASO₄. A broad diffraction pattern at 2 θ angle of scale 22° was seen. This indicates that the catalysts have an amorphous nature [64, 65].

Fig. 3.12: The XRD diffraction pattern for RHASO₄. (a) XRD of 5% RHASO₄. (b) XRD of 10% RHASO₄. (c) XRD of 15% RHASO₄. (d) XRD of 20% RHASO₄.

3.2 Preparation of RHAP₄

The description of a direct synthesis of phosphoric acid onto RHA surface to form the solid acid catalyst. The preparation of nano catalyst was carried out by the reaction between RHA and phosphoric acid with four different percentages of dilute phosphoric acid. A proposed structure for nano silica phosphoric acid showed in the scheme 3.2.

Scheme 3.2: A proposed structure for nano silica phosphoric acid [66, 67].

The catalyst is characterized by many techniques that will be mentioned in detail as below.

3.2.1 Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopic of RHAP₄

The FT-IR spectrum of RHAP₄ showed in Fig. 3.13 (a, b, c, and d), while table 3.3 shows the vibration of functional groups. The silanol group was observed at 3522-3404 cm⁻¹ in Fig. 3.1 (a). Fig. 3.1 (b, c, and d) for other loading of 5%RHAP₄ (10, 15, 20%) the silanol groups were observed at 3444-3325 cm⁻¹, 3431 cm⁻¹, and 3444 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The strong band at 1095 cm⁻¹ was due to the stretching vibration of Si-O-Si. This band was not changed due to the increase loading of H₃PO₄. The P=O stretch group for different loading of RHAP₄ was observed at 1320-1140 cm⁻¹[61]. This band was not changed due to the different loading of H₃PO₄ onto RHA. The PO₄⁻³ stretch group for different loading was observed at 1100-950 cm⁻¹ [68]. The P-O

stretch group for different loading was observed at 995 cm^{-1} [61]. This band was not changed due to the increased load of H_3PO_4 .

Table 3.3: FT-IR spectrophotometer results of RHAPo_4 .

Functional groups	Vibration of $5\% \text{RHAPo}_4$ cm^{-1}	Vibration of $10\% \text{RHAPo}_4$ cm^{-1}	Vibration of $15\% \text{RHAPo}_4$ cm^{-1}	Vibration of $20\% \text{RHAPo}_4$ cm^{-1}
Si-OH	3522-3404	3444-3325	3431	3444
Si-O-Si	1101	1095	1093	1095
Moisture in SiO_2	1641	1649	1639	1635
PO_4^{-3} stretch	1100-950	1007-950	1005-950	1050-950

Fig. 3.13: FT-IR spectrum of (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% RHAPo_4).

3.2.2 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) /Differential thermal analysis (DTA) for RHAPO₄

Figure 3.14 (a, b, c, and d) shows the that TGA/DTA graphs of the 5%RHAPO₄, 10%RHAPO₄, 15%RHAPO₄, and 20%RHAPO₄. The TGA analysis of 5%RHAPO₄ in Fig. 3.14 (a) showed three characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 1.7% at 120 °C due to the loss of surface absorbed water. The second mass loss was 2.1% at 219 °C. The third mass loss was 1.2% at 579 °C. The TGA analysis of 10%RHAPO₄ in Fig. 3.14 (b) showed three characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 2.9% at 106 °C as a result of loss surface absorbed water. The second mass loss was 4.9% at 201°C. The third mass loss was 1.5% at 600 °C. While the TGA analysis of 15%RHAPO₄ in Fig. 3.14 (c) showed four characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 2.5% at 134 °C. The second mass loss was 2.6% at 204°C. The third mass loss was 5.4% at 248°C. The fourth mass loss was 2.3% at 550 °C. TGA analysis of 20%RHAPO₄ in Fig. 3.14 (d) showed three characteristic decomposition stages. The first mass loss was 4.9% at 120 °C. The second mass loss was 6.2% at 219 °C. The third mass loss was 3.7% at 579 °C. Fig. 3.14 (a, b, c, d) it was concluded that the percentage mass loss of increases with increasing the percentage of acid loading onto silica.

The DTA curve shown in figures 3.14 (a, b, c, and d) shows exothermic transformation. The DTA curve for 5%RHAPO₄ in Fig. 3.14 (a) shows three exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs in the range of 40-167 °C with maximum at 120 °C. The second exothermic occurs at 167-314°C with maximum of 219 °C, and the third exothermic occurs in the range 540-650 °C with maximum at 579 °C. The DTA curve for 10%RHAPO₄ in Fig. 3.14 (b) shows two exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs in the range 39 -149 °C with

maximum at 106 °C. The second exothermic occurs at 149-276°C with maximum at 201 °C. The DTA curve for 15%RHAP₄ in Fig. 3.14 (c) shows three exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs in the range in the range 40 -171 °C with maximum at 134 °C. The second exothermic occurs at 171-219°C with maximum of 204 °C, and the third exothermic occurs in the range 219-335 °C with maximum at 248°C. The DTA curve for 20%RHAP₄ in Fig. 3.14 (d) shows third exothermic transformations. The first exothermic occurs in the range 40 -167 °C with maximum at 120 °C. While the second exothermic occurs at 167-314°C with maximum of 219 °C, and the third exothermic occurs at 530-650 °C with maximum at 579 °C.

Fig. 3.14 (a): TGA / DTA for 5% RHAP₄.

Fig. 3.14 (b): TGA / DTA for 10% RHAPO₄.

Fig. 3.14 (c): TGA / DTA for 15% RHAPO₄.

Fig. 3.14 (d): TGA / DTA for 20% RHAPO₄.

3.2.3 Nitrogen adsorption– desorption for different loading RHAPO₄

The N₂ adsorption– desorption analysis showed a specific surface area of 20% RHAPO₄ was 1.0 m² gm⁻¹, the specific surface area of 15% RHAPO₄ 12.33 m² gm⁻¹, while the specific surface area of 10% RHAPO₄ 29.46 m² gm⁻¹. The specific surface area was 31.87 m² gm⁻¹ for 5% RHAPO₄. Fig 3.15 (a, b, and c) shows the nitrogen adsorption isotherm for 5% RHAPO₄, 10% RHAPO₄, and 15% RHAPO₄, in which the shapes of hysteresis loops type H3 and do not exhibit any limiting adsorption at high P/P_o . This behavior caused by the existence of non-rigid aggregates of plate-like particles or of slit-shaped pores and in principle should not be expected to provide a reliable assessment of either the pore size distribution or the total pore volume [63].

The other catalyst of 20% RHAPO₄ gives isotherms type H4 hysteresis loops which was generally observed with complex materials containing both micropores

and mesopores. Both, types H3 and H4 hysteresis contain a characteristic step-down in the desorption branch associated with the hysteresis loop closure [63].

The pore size distribution of 5% RHAPO_4 was found 1.29 nm. The pore size distribution of 10% RHAPO_4 was found 4.6 nm, while the pore size distribution of 15% RHAPO_4 was found 4.45 nm. The pore size distribution of 20% RHAPO_4 was found 4.5 nm. The information on the Nitrogen adsorption– desorption analysis was shown in Table 3.4, and Fig 3.15.

Fig.3.15. The nitrogen adsorption– desorption isotherm of (a) 5% RHAPo_4 , (b) 10% RHAPo_4 , (c) 15% RHAPo_4 , and (d) 20% RHAPo_4 .

Table 3.4: The nitrogen adsorption– desorption parameter for different loading of RHAPO₄.

Sample	Surface area (m ² /gm)	Average pore diameter (nm)	Average pore volume (cm ³ /gm)
5% RHAPO ₄	2.51	1.29	0.01
10% RHAPO ₄	18.04	4.6	0.07
15% RHAPO ₄	39.53	2.45	0.13
20% RHAPO ₄	41.39	2.45	0.12

3.2.4.1 TEM for 5%RHAPO₄

As shown in Fig. (3.16), the TEM for both images (a, and b) at 100 nm, the porous and hollow layer of RHA nanoreactors with 5% H₃PO₄. Fig. (3.16) the TEM for images (c, and d) for 5% RHAPO₄ showed that the particles were irregular and correlated cluster grids.

Fig. 3.16: TEM at 75, 100 nm, the porous and hollow layer of RHA nanoreactors with 5% H_3PO_4 [69].

3.2.4.2 TEM for 10%RHAP₄

TEM images for 10% RHAP₄ showed that the particles were irregular and correlated cluster grids as in Fig 3.17 (a, and b).

Fig. 3.17: TEM images for 10% RHAP₄.

3.2.4.3 TEM for 15%RHAP₄

Fig. 3.18 (a, and b), the TEM images for 15% RHAP₄, showed the particles were irregular and correlated cluster grids. Fig. 3.18 (c, and d) shows spherical nanoparticles arranged randomly. The size of particles were less than 50 nm.

Fig. 3.18(a, b): The TEM images for 15% RHAP₄.

Fig. 3.18(c, d): The TEM images for 15% RHAPO₄.

3.2.4.4 TEM for 20%RHAPO₄

Fig. 3.19 (a, and b), the TEM for both images, the porous and cavity layer of 20%H₃PO₄ was observed Fig. 3.19 (c, and d) the TEM images for 20% RHAPO₄ showed the particles were irregular and spherical nanoparticles.

Fig. 3.19 (a, b): The TEM images for 20% RHAPO₄.

Fig. 3.19(c, d): The TEM images for 20% RHAPO₄.

3.2.5.1 SEM for 5%RHAPO₄

Fig. 3.20 (a, b, c, and d) shows the SEM of 5%RHAPO₄. Fig. 3.20 (a) show that the SEM of 5%RHAPO₄ of the surface was rough and rock shapes are arranged randomly onto surface. Fig. 3.20 (b, c, and d). The surface doesn't show any specific shapes. Only group particles were seen onto surface.

Fig. 3.20: The SEM images for 5%RHAPO₄ images show that the topographic map of the catalyst surface.

3.2.5.2 SEM for 10%RHAP₄

The SEM of 10%RHAP₄ in Fig. 3.21 (c, and e) showed the rough surface with particles in rock shapes were seen. While Fig. 3.21 (a, b, d, and f) showed a smooth surface without any specific shapes.

Fig. 3.21: The SEM images for 10%RHAP₄.

3.2.5.3 SEM for 15%RHAP₄

Fig. 3.22 (a, b, c, d, e, and f) shows the SEM of 15%RHAP₄. Fig. 3.22 (a) shows rock particle distributed randomly on the surface. The particles were show slight agglomerating nature to each others.

Fig. 3.22: The SEM images for 15%RHAP₄.

3.2.5.4 SEM for 20%RHAP₄

Fig. 3.23 (a, b, c, and d) shows an SEM of 20% RHAP₄. A granular surface was seen in fig. 3.23 (a, b, c, and d). The particles were spherical in shape with different nano size.

Fig. 3.23: The SEM images for 20%RHAP₄.

3.2.6 X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis for RHAPO₄

XRD pattern analysis is used to monitor the scattering intensity of the X-ray beam at the angle of fall and scattering. Fig. 3.24 (a, b, c, and d) shows the XRD pattern of (5, 10, 15, and 20) %RHAPO₄. A broad diffraction pattern at a 2θ angle of scale 22° was seen. This indicates that the catalysts have an amorphous nature [64, 65].

Fig. 3.24: The XRD diffraction pattern for RHAPO₄. (a) XRD of 5% RHAPO₄. (b) XRD of 10% RHAPO₄. (c) XRD of 15% RHAPO₄. (d) XRD of 20% RHAPO₄.

Chapter Four
Catalytic Activity,
Conclusions, and
Recommendations

4.0 Catalytic Performances

4.1 Catalytic Activity of Catalyst

The catalysts were applied as a nitrous ion generator and a carrier for the preparing diazonium salt. The aniline was treated with the catalyst in the water at laboratory temperatures. The sodium nitrite solution was added drop-drop to the aniline-catalyst mixture. After the formation of diazonium salt, simple filtration was necessary to remove the catalyst. The final reaction was the coupling of the diazonium salt with α -naphthol as a model substrate to form azo dyes as in Scheme (4.1), schem (4.2), and scheme (4.3).

Schematic 4.1: Preparation (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) over RHASO₄.

Scheme 4-2: Preparation (4-Nitro-2-phenylazo-phenol) over 20%RHASO₄.

Scheme 4-3: Preparation (4-hydroxy-1-[4-(hydroxyphenyl)-azo]naphthalene) over 20%RHASO₄.

4.1.1 Influence of Acid Loading

The activity of RHASO₄ was analyzed at different loading of catalyst. Different loading of RHASO₄ were used (5% RHASO₄, 10% RHASO₄, 15% RHASO₄, and 20% RHASO₄) to obtain the best active loading of catalyst as in Table 4.1 and (Fig. 4.1). The yield obtained is reached to its maximal of 42.5% when the reaction is carried out by using 0.1 gm of 20% RHASO₄ at 0-5 °C. Other catalyst were shown low yield. Therefore 20% RHASO₄ was choosing as optimum loading of sulfuric acid onto silica.

Table 4.1: The effects of different loading of sulfuric acid onto RHA on the production of (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) at 0-5 °C.

No.	Catalyst	% Yield
1	5% RHASO ₄	40
2	10% RHASO ₄	37
3	15% RHASO ₄	35
4	20% RHASO ₄	42.5

Fig. 4.1: The effects of different H_2SO_4 loading onto RHA.

About 0.1 gm of catalyst is used at 0-5 °C.

4.1.2 The influence of catalyst mass

The activity of 20%RHASO₄ was analyzed at different mass of catalyst. Four different mass of 20%RHASO₄ (0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25 gm) were used to obtain the optimum mass of catalyst. The yield obtained reached to the maximal of 65.5% when the reaction is carried out by using the 0.25 gm at 0-5 °C. It was observed that the azo yield was decreased when the catalyst mass was decreased too.

Table 4.2: The effects of catalyst mass on (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

No.	Mass (gm)	Yield %
1	0.10	42.5
2	0.15	50.5
3	0.20	55
4	0.25	65.5

Fig. 4.2: The effect catalyst mass on (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

4.1.3 The temperature effects

The activity of 20% RHASO_4 was analyzed at different temperature of the catalyst. Three different temperatures were used (5, 10, and 15 °C) to obtain the optimum temperature of the reaction. About 67.95% of azo dyes yield was obtain when the reaction is carried out by using 0.25 gm of 20% RHASO_4 at 10 °C. Similarly finding was mention study by [Hello and Fahad, 2019] [68]. These results show that it can produce azo dyes at temperature higher than the usual (0-5) °C.

Table 4.3: The effects reaction temperature onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

No.	Temperature °C	Yield %
1	5	65.5
2	10	67.95
3	15	65

Fig. 4.3: The effects of different temperatures onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) formation.

4.1.4 The solvent effect

The activity of 20%RHASO₄ was analyzed at different solvents. Five solvents were used (water, methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, and n-butanol) to obtain the suitable solvent for the coupling reaction over 20%RHASO₄. The results were as shown in Table 4.4, and Fig. 4.4. The yield obtained was 67.95% when the reaction was carried out by using water. Other solvent was shown a less yield than water.

Table 4.4: The effects of different solvents onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) over 20%RHASO₄. The reaction is carried out by using the 0.25 gm at 5 °C.

No.	Solvents	Yield %
1	Water	67.95
2	Methanol	52
3	Ethanol	45
4	1-propanol	57
5	n-butanol	54.85

Fig. 4.4: The effects of different solvents onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

4.1.5 Reusability Study of 20%RHASO₄ Using Water and Methanol

The catalytic reusability result was shown in Table 4.5 and (Fig. 4.5). From the results of the reusability it was clearly shown that the catalyst is stable during the course of running without losing of its activity.

Table 4.5: The reusability experiments of 20%RHASO₄ onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

No.	Reusability	Yield % solvent methanol	Yield % solvent water
1	One time	52	65
2	Two times	55	57
3	Three times	52	62

Fig. 4.5: The reusability experiments of 20%RHASO₄ onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

4.1.6 FT-IR of Reused Catalyst 20%RHASO₄

The FT-IR spectrum of 20%RHASO₄ after use was shown in Fig. 4.6, and Table 4.6 which was listed the vibration of functional groups as compared to fresh catalyst.

Table 4.6: FT-IR results of fresh (Page 29) and reused catalyst.

Functional groups	Vibration of fresh catalyst cm ⁻¹ (page 36)	Vibration of catalyst after use (cm ⁻¹)
Si-OH	3416	3416
Si-O-Si	1095	1095
Moisture in SiO ₂	1649	1649
S -O stretch	885-794	885-794

Fig. 4.6: FT-IR spectrum of reused catalyst 20% RHASO₄.

4.2 Catalytic Activity of RHAPO₄

The catalytic activity of: 5% RHAPO₄, 10% RHAPO₄, 15% RHAPO₄, and 20 % RHAPO₄, were examine in the preparation of the azo dyes production as carrier of nitrous ion. Below the method used to reach the optimum conditions.

4.2.1 Influence of Acid Loading onto Activity of Catalyst

The activity of RHAPO₄ was analyzed at different loading of acid catalyst on to silica. Four different loading of RHAPO₄ were used (5% RHAPO₄, 10% RHAPO₄, 15% RHAPO₄, and 20% RHAPO₄) to obtain the best loading of catalyst. The results were listed as in the Table 4.7 and (Fig. 4.7). The obtained yield to it's maximal of 45% over 20% RHAPO₄ when the reaction carried out by using the 0.1 gm of 20% RHAPO₄ at 0-5 °C.

Table 4.7: The effects of different H₃PO₄ acid loading onto RHA on production of (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) at a temperature 0-5 °C.

No.	Catalyst	% Yield
1	5% RHAPO ₄	35
2	10% RHAPO ₄	37
3	15% RHAPO ₄	40
4	20% RHAPO ₄	45

Fig. 4.7: The effects of different H₃PO₄ acid loading onto RHA.

4.2.2 Mass Optimization of 20% RHAP₄

The activity of different catalyst mass was analyzed on the azo dyes synthesis. Four different mass of 20% RHAP₄ were used (0.1, 0.15, 0.2, and 0.25) gm to obtain the best catalyst mass. The obtained yield reached to the maximum of 75.5% when the reaction is carried out using 0.25 gm of 20% RHAP₄ at 0-5 °C. The increase of catalyst mass could be lead to increase the number of active center and this lead to increase the azo dyes yield. The result was discussed in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8: The mass effect onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) production.

No.	Mass (gm)	Yield %
1	0.10	45
2	0.15	47
3	0.20	67.5
4	0.25	75.5

Fig. 4.8: The effect of catalyst mass onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

4.2.3 The Effect of Reaction Temperature

The activity of 20%RHAP₄ was analyzed at different temperature of the catalyst. Three different temperatures were used (5, 10, and 15°C) to obtain the optimum temperature of the catalyst and the result was shown as in Table 4.9 (Fig. 4.9). The obtained yield to its maximal of 85% when the reaction was carried by out using the 0.25 gm at 10 °C. In a previous study by [Hello and Fahad, 2019] [70], it was found that the azo dyes could prepare at 10 °C with high yield. Similarly 20% RHASO₄ was give high yield at 10 °C.

Table 4.9: The effects reaction temperature onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) production over 20% RHAP₄.

No.	Temperature °C	Yield %
1	5	75.5
2	10	85
3	15	63.5

Fig. 4.9: The effects of different temperatures onto azo dyes formation.

4.2.4 Solvents Effect

The activity of 20%RHAP₄ on the azo dyes formation was examined at different solvents. Five different solvents were used (water, methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol, and n-butanol) to obtain the best solvent lead to high yield of azo dyes. The results were shown in Table 4.10, and (Fig. 4.10). The obtained yield was 85% when the reaction is carried out by using the 0.25 gm at 10 °C in water. The n-butanol was also show high yield of azo dye. Other solvents were shown good yield of azo dyes.

Table 4.10: Effects of different solvents onto (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol) over 20% RHAP₄.

No.	Solvents	Yield %
1	Water	85
2	Methanol	52
3	Ethanol	54
4	1-Propanol	54
5	n-Butanol	80

Fig. 4.10: The effects of different solvents onto 4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

4.2.5 Reusability Study of 20%RHAP₄ Using the Solvent n-Butanol and Water

The catalytic reusability was given in Table 4.11 and (Fig. 4.11). The reusability was examined in two different solvents. The catalyst show similar conversion of product during the course of running. This indicated that the catalyst was stable and may not lose its activity during the used three times. Except the use of the catalyst for the third time using a water solvent was observed a decrease in the yield of azo dye. This can be caused by catalyst poisoning and consequently a decrease in active centers.

Table 4.11: The reusability experiments of 20%RHAP₄ onto production of (4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

No.	Reusability	Yield % solvent n-butanol	Yield % solvent water
1	One time	80.4	85
2	Two times	73	82
3	Three times	82	67

Fig. 4.11: The reusability experiments of 20%RHAP₄ onto 4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol).

4.2.6 FT-IR Analysis of Reused Catalyst 20%RHAP₄

The FT-IR spectrum of 20%RHAP₄ after using it as a catalyst, shown in Table 4.12, and Fig. 4.12. Functional groups of catalyst are existent as compared to fresh catalyst.

Table 4.12: FT-IR spectrophotometer results of fresh (page 47) and reused catalyst.

Functional groups	Vibration of fresh catalyst cm ⁻¹ (page 56)	Vibration of catalyst after use (cm ⁻¹)
Si-OH	3444	3439
Si-O-Si	1095	1082
Moisture in SiO ₂	1635	1651
P -O ⁻ stretch	1110	1110
P=O stretch	1516	1516

Fig. 4.12: FT-IR spectrum of reused catalyst 20% RHAP₄.

4.3 Physical Properties of Azo Compound

Table 4.13 shows the properties of an azo compound which are prepared using catalyst. The physical data of azo dyes compared with the literatures.

Table 4.13: shows the structure, and physical properties of azo compound.

No. of Compound	Structure of Compound	Physical Properties
1	<p>4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol</p>	Red color is non-crystalline solid M.P Found 128-130 °C Liter. 132 °C. Yield 67.5% by using RHASO ₄ Yield 85% by using RHAPO ₄
2	<p>4-Nitro-2-phenylazo-phenol.</p>	Yellow crystalline solid Yield 79% by using RHASO ₄ Yield 87% by using RHAPO ₄
3	<p>4-hydroxy-1-[4-(hydroxyphenyl)-azo]naphthalene</p>	Purple M.P Found 176 °C Liter. 174 - 174.5 °C. Yield 67% by using RHAPO ₄

4.4 FT-IR Spectra

The FT-IR (sees Appendix 1-4) is listed in Table 4.16 the values of vibrations in the spectrum for each azo compound were discusses carefully. The FT-IR shows the presence of N=N at the expected position.

Table 4.14: The most significant values of functional group in the spectrum for each azo compound.

No. compound	Functional group
1	OH stretch at 3475 cm^{-1} , C-H aromatic stretch at 3070 cm^{-1} , C-N stretch at 1660 cm^{-1} , C-O stretch at 1255 cm^{-1} , C=C aromatic stretch at 1597 cm^{-1} , N=N at 1471 cm^{-1} .
2	OH stretch at $3200\text{-}3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-H aromatic stretch at 3000 cm^{-1} , C-N stretch at 1653 cm^{-1} , C-O stretch at 1255 cm^{-1} , C=C aromatic stretch at 1600 cm^{-1} , N=N at 1491 cm^{-1} , N-O stretch at 1303 cm^{-1} , 1589 cm^{-1} .
3	OH stretch at $3387\text{-}3521\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-H aromatic stretch at 3061 cm^{-1} , C-N stretch at 1653 cm^{-1} , C-O stretch at 1255 cm^{-1} , C=C aromatic stretch at 1593 cm^{-1} , N=N at 1448 cm^{-1} .

4.5 Conclusions

- 1- Solid acid catalyst has been prepared by loaded of sulfuric acid and phosphoric acid onto the silica surface of RH at eight different percentage loaded structures.
- 2- Spectroscopic techniques such as FT-IR, TGA/DTA, SEM, TEM, Nitrogen adsorption-desorption, and XRD. Prove that nanoparticles are included in new preparation catalysts at different shapes with an amorphous structure.
- 3- Optimum condition of the silica sulfuric acid show by using 0.25 gm of 20%RHASO₄ at 5°. On the other hand, Optimum condition of the silica phosphoric acid show by using 0.25 gm of 20%RHAPO₄ at 10°.
- 4- High yield percentage of azo dyes production by using 20% of both RHASO₄ and RHAPO₄ under optimum condition.

4.6 Recommendations

- 1- Using other mineral acids as a proposal for future work
- 2- Using new percentages in preparing and testing the catalyst.
- 3- Study the reaction mechanism for releasing the nitrite ion in the diazonium reaction.
- 4- The experiment and test of the effective experiment in the experience of the previous experiment in the experiment of high thermal stability, such as various oxidation and reduction reactions.

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Appendix

Characterization of azo dyes - the catalyst RHASO_4 and RHAPSO_4

Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopic Analysis

Appendix 1: FT-IR Spectrum of 4-(phenyl azo)-1-Naphthol

Appendix 2: FT-IR Spectrum of 2-hydroxy-5-nitroazobenzene

Appendix 3: FT-IR Spectrum of 4-hydroxy-1-[4-(hydroxyphenyl)azo] naphth-alene.

الخلاصة

في هذه الدراسة، تم استخلاص السيليكا من قشور الرز، ومن ثم تم تحريكها مع حامض الكبريتيك المخفف و حامض الفسفوريك لمدة 24 ساعة في درجة حرارة الغرفة. تم تحميل تراكيز مختلفة من الحامض على السليكا المحضرة، تضمنت RHASO_4 X% RHASO_4 حيث X هي : (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%). شخّصت العوامل المساعدة المحضرة بالعديد من التقنيات تضمنت مطيافية الأشعة تحت الحمراء FT-IR، و حيود الأشعة السينية XRD، و التحليل الوزني الحراري TGA / DTA، و تحليل امتزاز- ابتزاز النتروجين، و المجهر الإلكتروني الماسح SEM، و المجهر الإلكتروني النافذ TEM. أظهرت مطيافية الأشعة تحت الحمراء FT-IR كل المجاميع الوظيفية المتوقعة لكل عامل مساعد. تحليل حيود الأشعة السينية أظهر حزمة عريضة عند 2θ بزواية 22° ذلك يشير الى طبيعة العامل المساعد غير البلورية. اظهرت نتيجة التحليل الوزني الحراري TGA / DTA ان العوامل المساعدة تكون مستقرة عند درجة حرارة اعلى من 180°C . اظهرت صورالمجهر الإلكتروني الماسح SEM ان سطح العامل المساعد تضمن اشكال أسطوانية، و بعضها حبيبية، والبعض الاخر كروية. بينما اظهرت صور المجهر الإلكتروني النافذ TEM جسيمات بأحجام نانوية مختلفة، بعض الجسيمات النانوية لها طبقة مجوفة مسامية والبعض الاخر لها أشكال كروية. تم دراسة الفعالية التحفيزية لكل عامل مساعد بأعتباره مادة مولدة وحاملة لأيون النتريت في تحضير حامض النيتروز الذي أستخدم لتحضير أصباغ الأزو. تم تحليل فعالية RHASO_4 ، و RHASO_4 عند تحميل مختلف للمحفزات للحصول على تحميل بأفضل فعالية. وجد أن 20% RHASO_4 وصلت الى أقصى حد لها 65.5%، بينما وصلت الى 75.5% بأستخدام 20% RHASO_4 . حيث تم إجراء التفاعل باستخدام 0.25 gm عند درجة 10°C من كلا العاملين المساعدين.

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الرُّوحِ ^{صَلِّ عَلَى} قُلِّ الرُّوحِ مِنْ
أَمْرِ رَبِّي وَمَا أُوتِيتُمْ مِنَ الْعِلْمِ إِلَّا قَلِيلًا

صَدَقَ اللَّهُ الْعَلِيُّ الْعَظِيمُ

(الأسراء آية 85)

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
جامعة المثنى / كلية العلوم
قسم الكيمياء

دراسة تحضير و تشخيص كبريتات و فوسفات السيليكا كعامل مساعد محفز لأيون النترت وتطبيقاتها في تكوين مركبات الآزو

رسالة مقدمة كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجة الماجستير في علوم الكيمياء

من قبل

الهام كاظم هلال

بإشراف

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